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The Effect of Potassium Diformate Addition to the Growth Rate and the Activity of Protease Enzyme of Giant Gourami Fingerlings (*Osphronemus goramy* Lacepede, 1801)

Ayi Yustiati*, Algi Azmi Nugraha, Ibnu Bangkit Bioshina, Yuli Andriani

Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Sciences, Padjadjaran University,
Bandung – Sumedang KM.21 Jatinangor 45363, Indonesia

*E-mail address: yustiati@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the effect of adding potassium diformate to commercial feed on the increase of absolute growth rate and the activity of protease enzyme. The research was conducted from July to October 2019 in the Aquaculture Laboratory Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Sciences, Padjadjaran University. The method applied in this research was an experimental method using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD), which consists of four treatments and four replications. The treatments were: (A) without addition of Potassium diformate (control), (B) addition of Potassium diformate by 0.3%, (C) addition of Potassium diformate by 0.5%, and (D) addition Potassium diformate by 0.8%. The test fish were 300 giant gouramis with 4-6 cm in length. The containers used in this research were 16 rearing aquaria with a size of 40 × 30 × 40 cm³. The density of studied giant gourami fingerlings was 10 fish per aquarium. The rearing period was 40 days. The feeding rate was 3% from biomass. Water quality parameters (temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen), the absolute growth rate, feed conversion ratio and survival rate were observed every 10 days. The protease enzyme activities were observed at the end of the research. Data on the absolute growth rate, feeding conversion ratio, the characteristics of protease enzyme and survival rate were analyzed using the *Analysis of Variance* (ANNOVA) continued with Duncan's Multiple Range Test at the level of 95%, while the water quality was analyzed descriptively. The results show that the addition of potassium diformate by 0.3% gave the best result with the absolute growth rate of 1.50%, feed conversion ratio of 2.70, protease enzyme activity by 634.2 µ/mL and survival rate of 100%.

Keywords: potassium diformate, giant gourami, growth, protease enzyme, *Osphronemus goramy*

1. INTRODUCTION

Giant gourami fish (*Osphronemus goramy* Lacepede, 1801) is a superior commodity of the freshwater fish farming. Gourami can breed naturally and have a good economic value, so that many farmers are interested to culture gourami as a livelihood. The growth of gourami is slower compared to other types of freshwater fish. The factors that affect growth rates are less intensive maintenance, poor quality of gourami fingerlings, and the type of feeding that does not support fish growth. The change from insectivore into omnivores at the age of eight months slows the growth of gourami. One way to overcome this is by giving potassium diformate. Based on the Commission Regulation of the European Communities (EC) 1334/2001, potassium diformate has been registered as a promoter of non-antibiotic growth with the aim of replacing antibiotics in feed, to ensure the products produced are safe for consumers. Potassium diformate has ingredients that can encourage animal growth. Formatted potassium also diffuses with pathogenic bacteria in the digestive tract and acidifies the metabolism, which can kill the pathogenic bacteria. Potassium diformate contains beneficial bacteria (Lactobacilli and Bifidobacteria) which can balance the population of bacteria in the digestive tract, so as to cause an increase in intestinal health.

The addition of 0.2% to 0.5% of the formatted potassium can significantly improve feed efficiency, increase growth performance, reduce the number of pathogenic bacteria in the digestive tract, leaving behind no residue to the fish or to the environment. Potassium diformate has a similar antimicrobial effect against other types of bacteria, such as *E. coli*. Adding formatted potassium to feed will reduce pathogenic bacteria present in the feed which leads to the feed absorption and increasing growth rates. Antimicrobial effect in the formatted potassium is the main beneficial factor. Strong antimicrobial which derived from a high concentration of phosphoric acid and lactic acid are useful to reduce the pH value. The usage of formatted potassium in the feed can improve feed efficiency, increase the performance of growth and kill pathogenic bacteria in the intestine so as to optimize the growth rate.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted in the Aquaculture Laboratory Building 4, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Sciences, Padjadjaran University from July to October 2019. The instruments used were aquaria measuring 40 cm × 30 cm × 40 cm, fiber tanks measuring 2 m × 1 m × 1 m, DO meters, pH meters, digital scales, millimeter blocks, aeration equipment, laboratory equipment for mixing potassium diformate into the feed, measuring cups, sprayers and trays. The materials used were 300 gourami fish with 4-6 grams in size, potassium diformate and granular commercial fish feed.

The experimental design conducted in this research was a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) consisting of four treatments and four replications, namely:

Treatment A: Commercial feed with the addition of potassium diformate as much as 0%.

Treatment B: Commercial feed with the addition of potassium diformate as much as 0.3%.

Treatment C: Commercial feed with the addition of potassium diformate as much as 0.5%.

Treatment D: Commercial feed with the addition of potassium diformate as much as 0.8%.

2. 1. Experimental Units

The gourami fingerlings that would be treated were acclimatized for 5 days in fiber containers which were given aeration and commercial feed. There were 16 fish kept in the aquarium equipped with aeration and heater. The fish were fed twice a day, in the morning at 08.00 West Indonesia Time and in the evening at 17.00 West Indonesia Time, using a mix of test feed which was 3% of fish biomass and potassium diformate with different amounts in each treatment, according to the research methods. The siphoning was done every day and the water volume was replaced by 10% to maintain water quality during rearing. The fish were reared for 40 days.

2. 2. Experimental Fish

Three hundred gourami fingerlings that were studied with initial weights of 4-6 grams were obtained from the Southern Ocean and Fisheries Service Office Branch Tasikmalaya, West Java. The criteria for the studied fish were homogeneous and healthy body weight.

2. 3. Experimental Diets

The nutritional content of the commercial feed used had to follow the needs of 4-6 gram gourami fish. The steps of adding potassium diformate into commercial feed are, add potassium diformate into the feed, stir until it became homogeneous, after that spray with 10% of water in order to bound the formulated potassium to the feed, then dry with aeration, the feed is then ready to be given to the gourami fish. Feed that has been given potassium diformate must be completely dry because a wetness will cause mold. Feed mixing was carried out once every 10 days.

2. 4. Experimental Methodology

Gourami fingerlings were kept in aquaria as rearing containers with a density of 10 fish/aquarium. Fish were weighed once every 10 days to investigate the values of weight gain, feed efficiency and survival. The measurements of water quality in gourami habitat, namely, temperature, DO (Dissolved oxygen) and pH were done every 10 days to maintain the environment of the fish in accordance with the standard values required for the fish to live. Furthermore, the measurement of the stomach acidity was carried out at the beginning and at the end of treatment.

Observed parameters included:

Absolute Weight Growth Rate: **W = W_t – W₀**

Explanation:

W = Absolute weight growth rate

W_t = Final weight of gourami (g)

W₀ = Initial weight of gourami (g).

Absolute Length Growth Rate: **L = L_t – L₀**

Explanation:

- L = Absolute length growth rate
- L_t = Final length of gourami (cm)
- L₀ = Initial length of gourami (cm).

Feed Conversion Ratio:
$$FCR = \frac{F}{(W_t + D) - W_0} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

- FCR = Feed Conversion Ratio
- F = Amount of feed given during the research (g)
- W_t = Biomass at the end (g)
- W = Biomass at the beginning (g)
- D = Gourami biomass that died during the research (g).

Survival Rate:
$$SR = \frac{N_t}{N_0} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

- SR = Rate of Survival (%)
- N_t = Number of living fish at the end of treatment (individual)
- N₀ = The number of fish at the beginning of treatment (individual).

Activity of Protease Enzyme

At the end of the research, 3 fish from each treatment were randomly taken as samples to analyze the protease enzyme in the body of gourami. Protease activity was measured using the method of Kunitz (1971) with modifications. Insulation of the intestinal digestive tracts were done by fainting the gourami beforehand by soaking them in ice water. From digestive tracts that had been separated from the bodies, the intestine parts were taken, exactly at the part after the stomach. The digestive tracts were prepared in cold conditions on slabs of ice. Intestine samples were further divided into 3 segments (front, middle, and back intestines). After that, the samples were crushed in each section and then centrifuged at 6,000 rpm, 4 °C for 10 minutes and then the supernatant fractions were taken as samples. Samples were taken as much as 100 μL, added with a 0.1% casein substrate mixture of 500 μL and incubated for 60 minutes in a water bath at 37 °C. After incubation, the reaction was stopped by adding 500 mL of 10% TCA solution and distilled water up to 2 mL volume. The same procedures were performed on the blank. Tyrosine absorbance as a product of casein hydrolysis by protease activity was measured using a spectrophotometer at λ 280 nm.

$$Activity = \frac{Absorbance\ of\ Sample - Absorbance\ of\ Blanko}{0,001 \times Hidrolisis\ time\ (s) \times Volume\ enzymes\ (mL)}$$

Water Quality

Measurements of water quality in this research included temperature, DO (Dissolved Oxygen) and pH (temperature, DO and pH, respectively, measured with a thermometer, pH

meter, and DO meter). Data on water quality were analyzed descriptively according to the quality standards of SNI (Indonesian National Standard).

3. RESULTS

Based on the research activities, the following results were obtained:

Absolute Growth Rate

Figure 1. Absolute Weight Growth Rate Graphic

Figure 2. Absolute Length Growth Rate Graphic

The results show a significant effect on the growth of absolute weight but do not show any real effect on absolute length. The absolute weight growth value of gourami is in the range of 0.62 - 1.50 gram. The absolute length growth value of gourami is in the range of 0.14 - 0.77 cm. The growth value of absolute weight and absolute length of gourami can be seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

The highest absolute growth of gourami is in treatment B with absolute weight growth value of 1.50 grams and absolute length growth of 0.77 cm, then followed by treatment C with absolute weight growth value of 0.95 grams and absolute length growth of 0.54 cm, treatment A with absolute weight growth value of 0.72 gram and absolute length growth of 0.39 cm, and the lowest absolute growth rate is in treatment D with absolute weight growth value of 0.62 gram and absolute length growth of 0.14 cm.

The absolute weight growth value of treatments B and C can be said to be good compared to treatment A, because the 5 cm gourami is the slowest growing, only 0.75% for three months of maintenance. The reason is, in this research, digestive tract of the studied fish had begun to complete, but then at 4 months old, the gouramis experienced a transition in the feeding habits. Therefore, the provision of organic acids can lower the pH of the digestive tract and around the acidic environmental conditions, gastrointestinal tract will absorb more nutrients because it is in optimal condition. In acidic conditions, pepsin will be active and break down protein to release the peptide bond and form peptone in the digestive tract.

Pepsin enzyme will be at a pH value of 2 and is not active at pH values of more than 6.5, but pepsin is not completely denatured or not activated until pH 8 (Figs. 3 and 4). However, in the treatment D, the absolute weight growth value decreased by only 0.62 grams, this is because in the treatment D, the dose of the formatted potassium exceeded the recommended dosage of 0.2 to 0.5%, so that the energy for growth was used to balance the body's osmoregulation system in fish.

(a) Initial Weight of Fish

(b) Final of Weight Fish

Figure 3(a,b). Comparison of Gourami Weights During Research

(a) Initial Length of Fish

(b) Final Length of Fish

Figure 4(a,b). Comparison of Gourami Lengths During Research

Feed Conversion Ratio

The results show that the value of feed conversion ratio is in the range of 2.70 to 4.36. Feed conversion ratio values can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Feed Conversion Ratio Graphic

The lower the feed conversion ratio is the more efficient the feed is eaten and consumed by fish for growth. The addition of formatted potassium can reduce the value of the feed conversion ratio as evidenced by treatment B (potassium diformate 0.3%), which is

significantly different from other treatments (Figure 5). This is because a higher dose of potassium diformate in the feed will affect fish's osmoregulation system because potassium is formed as organic acid salts, which requires less energy for growth thus the rest of energy is used to balance the osmoregulation system of fish. Formassium formulated to kill the cells of pathogenic bacteria in the digestive tract and increase the number of commensal bacteria so that the nutrients contained in the feed can be easily absorbed and the feeding becomes more efficient the feed conversion ratio thus improved. Potassium diformate makes the digestive tract of animals become acidic. This can help to increase the enzymatic activity assimilated, increase feed intake and feed conversion into meat. Formatted potassium can also reduce harm and increase beneficial bacteria and decrease intestinal pH.

Activity of Protease-Enzyme

The results show that the activity of protease enzyme in gourami intestines is in the range of 369.1 - 634.2 μ /mL. The value of protease enzyme activity can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Protease Enzyme Activity

Gourami fingerlings need more protein-rich feed to support their growth and development. This is because protein-rich feed will be used as an energy source for metabolism, besides, protein is the main nutrient for body growth and maintenance. The optimal amount of protein will synergize with fish's growth, if the needs of body maintenance have been met. The results show that the highest value of protease enzyme activity is in the treatment B which is 634.2 μ / mL and the lowest is in treatment D which is 369.1 μ / mL. The presence of enzyme activity is a biological indicator of the ability of fish to digest their food. With high enzyme activity, the fish's physiology is able to well digest the nutrients from the feed given.

The presence of a high protease enzyme activity is related to the role of the pancreas in the secretion of enzyme in the growing phase fish. Pancreas in juvenile fish will be more active

in secreting digestive enzyme. The pancreas that secretes enzyme in small amounts causes the enzyme activity in the digestive tract to be low, conversely if there are a lot of secretions, the activity will increase. Protease enzyme is distributed along the digestive tract, namely the stomach, hepatopancreas, and intestine. A low pH value will produce the active pepsin enzyme which makes the digestive tract absorb more nutrients. This is caused by a formic acid which decreases the pH of the digestive tract. However, if the administration of potassium exceeds the recommended dose, it will decrease the enzyme activity as in treatment D.

Survival Rate

The results show that the survival rate of gourami is in the range of 90 – 100%. The daily growth rate of common gourami fish can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Survival Rate Graphic

Based on the observations made within 40 days, the highest survival rate is in treatment B with 0.3% addition of potassium diformate which is equal to 100% (Figure 7). Adding potassium diformate to fish feed has an effect, though not significantly (only a tendency) to the survival rate of gourami fish because the control treatment and the experimental treatment do not show significantly different values. Other than that, the survival rate in this research is above 90% which is considered quite high. The survival rate of gourami fish that is not significantly different for each treatment and is within a very good range, can be caused by the positive reaction of fish to feed that contains potassium diformate. This is marked by the consumption of feed with the addition of potassium diformate. Besides, the feed factors, environmental conditions also affect the survival rate of gourami fish, because the environmental conditions set for the study followed the standards of gourami fish culture according to the Indonesian Nasional Standard.

The existence of fish mortality that occurs during the treatment is allegedly due to stress because the rearing media used for the research were aquaria in a laboratory, compared to the previous treatments which were at outdoor ponds. This happened because gourami fish has a sensitivity to stress shown by the movement of fish that were very active when removed from the water. After all, it is known that stress can reduce feed absorption, weaken the fish and affect spawning success. The survival rate of gourami fish is not significantly different for each treatment due to the positive response of fish to feed. This is marked by the amount of test feed eaten during research. This indicates that the addition of potassium diformate in commercial feed by 0.3%, 0.5%, and 0.8% has no negative effect on the survival of gourami fish fingerlings.

Water Quality

Water as the medium of fish's life must qualify the parameters of suitability, because water quality can influence the growth of aquatic organisms. The results of average water quality measurements can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Water Quality Measurement Result.

Parameter	Unit	Range Value	*Quality Standards
Temperature	°C	26 – 30	25 – 30
pH	-	6.38 – 7.30	6.5 – 8.5
DO	Mg/L	6.5 – 7.10	> 4

*According to Indonesian National Standard (SNI) 2000.

Based on the measurement results, the temperature range in aquarium treatment was between 26 – 30 °C; this range is still within the range of the standard quality temperature according to SNI for gourami fish, which are 25 – 30 °C. The temperature affects the response of fish to feed. The optimum water temperature of the rearing media can optimize the fish's response to feed. However, if the temperature is less or more than the optimum temperature range, the fish's response to feed will decrease. Temperature values are related to the dissolved oxygen (DO) values in the aquarium water. The higher the temperature of the water, the lower the solubility of oxygen in water, and vice versa. When the temperature is optimum, the dissolved oxygen will also be optimum. Dissolved oxygen becomes one of the determining factors of fish's life in water.

Dissolved oxygen is used for metabolic processes in the body of the fish, therefore the lack of dissolved oxygen will threaten the life of the fish. The content of dissolved oxygen, which is good for fish farming, ranges from 4-9 mg / L. The value of dissolved oxygen during the research was still in the normal range, which is 6.5 - 7.10 mg / L. This shows that the fish's need for dissolved oxygen was fulfilled during the research.

The degree of acidity (pH) of water in the rearing aquarium ranged from 6.38 - 7.30. The pH of water in the aquaria was suitable for gourami culture, the standard quality limit for gourami pH is 6.5 - 8.5.

Also, the degree of acidity that is good for the growth of fish and aquatic organisms is between 6.5 to 8.5. The pH value will affect the growth of fish because fish's appetite is reduced at low pH. A low pH value can cause clumping of mucus in the gills and the fish will suffocate so that the food consumed is used more as energy to maintain the body rather than for growth. The effect of pH varies, depending on the species and size of the fish and the temperature.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion that can be drawn from this research is that the optimum dosage of the addition of potassium diformate is 0.3% in order to produce the highest absolute weight and length growth value of 1.50 grams and 0.77 cm, the lower feed conversion ratio of 2.70, protease enzyme activity of 634.2 μ / mL and the highest survival of 100%.

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